

Uzbekistan's cooperation with the countries of the world is at a new stage

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Abstract: In this article, the great opportunities that the Republic of Uzbekistan is creating for citizens of foreign countries and its close relations with neighboring countries, including the past, history and present strong ties of the Uzbek and Kazakh peoples, including the social- joint efforts in political and economic direction were mentioned.

This article is recommended for reading by the general public.

Key words: adopted presidential decrees, the principle of equality before the law, values, strong neighborliness

Raising the culture of tolerance and humanity in society, ensuring international and inter-confessional solidarity, harmony of citizens, as well as strengthening friendly, equal and mutually beneficial relations with foreign countries is one of the priorities of the state policy of Uzbekistan.

These are necessary in order to respect and develop the principles of equality of citizens before the law, regardless of race, nationality, language, faith, personality and social origin, as well as the language, customs and traditions of representatives

of different nationalities and peoples, which are enshrined in our Constitution. based on the creation of conditions.

Strengthening the atmosphere of friendship and harmony, peace and stability in the society is an important factor and a necessary condition for the consistent implementation of reforms in the social, political, legal, economic, humanitarian and spiritual spheres, and for further increasing the prestige of our country in the international arena.

Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures to further improve international relations and friendly relations with foreign countries" to ensure stability, peace and harmony in society, belonging to a large, multinational single family in the minds of citizens It is aimed at strengthening the feeling, comprehensively supporting and further developing the activities of national cultural centers and friendship societies, and expanding cultural and educational relations with foreign countries.

In particular, the establishment of the Committee on International Relations and Friendship with Foreign Countries under the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan on the basis of the Republican International Cultural Center and the Council of Societies of Friendship and Cultural-Educational Relations of Uzbekistan with Foreign Countries is of great importance. earns.

The past, history and present of the Uzbek and Kazakh peoples are closely related to each other. The history, language, customs, traditions and values of the two peoples, who have been living peacefully and harmoniously as close neighbors since time immemorial, are similar. Diplomatic relations between the two countries

were established on November 23, 1992. In 1998, the Eternal Friendship Agreement was signed. With the signing of the Strategic Partnership Agreement in June 2013, the level of relations between the countries increased.

In recent years, the friendly neighborhood and strategic cooperation between the two countries has been steadily developing, relying on the commonality of language, religion, tradition, literature, and culture. As a clear example of this, on June 30, 2023, according to the decision of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 849, the decision to ratify the agreement on demarcation of the border of the two countries further strengthened the friendly relations of the two countries. In today's global world, close relations and open communication are appearing in new forms. The two countries have many mutual interests.

They also support each other in international political issues. For example, the Chairman of the Ministry of Emergencies of the Republic of Kazakhstan said that "the flood that started in the beginning of April in the Republic of Kazakhstan had not been such a tragic event for the Kazakh people in the last 30 years." In such difficult times, the initiative of the leader of our country and the long history of our people, the rich past, and the events happening in the neighboring country of our own people were indifferent. Our kind-hearted and generous people did not tire of giving their high qualities, friendship, and support in such a difficult time. Today, the whole world recognizes the exemplary qualities of the Uzbek people with their friendly and cooperative relations. We think that there are many people who have not seen videos showing the help of citizens on social networks.

Our countries have been effectively cooperating bilaterally and within the framework of a number of prestigious structures such as the United Nations, OSCE,

Shanghai Cooperation Organization, Commonwealth of Independent States, Organization of Islamic Cooperation, and the International Fund for Saving the Island.

The inter-parliamentary dialogue between Uzbekistan and Kazakhstan has become much more active. In order to study the experiences of the parties in the framework of law-making, including international parliamentary structures, mutual visits of delegations are carried out on a regular basis, and these are also reported by mass media.

Today, more than 800,000 compatriots of the Kazakh nationality live in Uzbekistan. The Uzbek community in Kazakhstan is more than 600,000 people. They serve the development and prosperity of the two countries, strengthening the ties of friendship and brotherhood between our peoples.

As a result of the political will of the Presidents of the two countries and the wise long-term policies implemented, multifaceted cooperative relations between our countries have reached a new level. Great success has been achieved in all areas, and large-scale cooperation is developing rapidly. Especially in recent years, the bilateral relations between these two countries have become active and reached a new level, and historical results are being achieved. In particular, political, cultural and economic dialogues are becoming more active, trade-industry and economic and investment relations are also expanding.

Uzbekistan and Kazakhstan: a new era in alliance relations

Uzbekistan is on the way to developing relations based on mutual trust and good neighborliness with the countries of Central Asia, including Kazakhstan. The

Uzbek and Kazakh peoples, not only as close neighbors, but also as brothers, have long understood and supported each other on all issues of multilateral cooperation. The countries are walking shoulder to shoulder on the path of development as good neighbors and mutually beneficial partners. Issues of fundamental expansion of relations in political, trade-economic, energy, agriculture, water and other spheres became the main topic of today.

Significant success in all areas of cooperation in recent years is a clear example of our words. Dialogues between the governments, ministries and departments, regions of the two countries have become regular. The President of our country, Shavkat M. Mirziyoyev, and the President of Kazakhstan Kasim-Jomart Tokayev, during their visit to our country on December 21-22, 2022, confirmed that the desire to continue mutually beneficial cooperation within the framework of multilateral structures is determined. locked

It was noted that such events serve to strengthen our friendship ties and show the great interest of the Uzbek people in the history of the brotherly Kazakh people. In general, this visit was a historic event that opened a new page in bilateral relations in terms of the breadth of the agenda of the high-level talks and the importance of the agreements reached.

The President expressed his gratitude to Shavkat Mirziyoyev for the construction policy and his great contribution to strengthening Kazakhstan-Uzbekistan relations. Emphasizing that he supports the constitutional reforms implemented at the initiative of the head of state, he expressed confidence that this reform will be a solid foundation for the development of Uzbekistan. It was

emphasized that the core of bilateral cooperation is the economy, and it is necessary to pay more attention to the use of the great potential of the two countries.

In particular, in the last five years, the volume of mutual trade has more than doubled, and by the end of this year it will reach five billion dollars. It was agreed to create a working group under the leadership of the Deputy Prime Ministers and establish a joint foreign trade company in order to increase the mutual supply of products in high demand in the coming years.

In conclusion, it should be noted that Uzbekistan is making special efforts to develop relations based on mutual trust and good neighborliness with the countries of Central Asia, including Kazakhstan. In particular, the above-mentioned works and today's reforms are all examples of our words. Uzbekistan and Kazakhstan: a new era, a new beginning in alliance relations. Judging from the above, it can be said that the Uzbek and Kazakh peoples have been brothers, born and lived as one people since time immemorial. Today's reforms will help to develop the prosperity and friendship of the two countries and take it to new heights.

References:

1. O'zbekiston Respublikasi Konstitutsiyasi 01.05.2023
2. O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining «Millatlararo munosabatlar va xorijiy mamlakatlar bilan do'stlik aloqalarini yanada takomillashtirish chora-tadbirlari to'g'risida» gi PF-5046-son Farmoni Toshkent sh., 2017-yil 19-may
3. Abadiy do'stlik to'g'risida O'RQ 31.10.1998

4. O'zbekiston va Qozog'iston hamkorligi yangi bosqichga chiqmoqda O'zLiDeP
Odinaxon OTAXONOVA O'zbekiston va Qozog'iston: ittifoqchilik
munosabatlarida yangi davr

5. O'zbekiston va Qozog'iston: ittifoqchilik munosabatlarida yangi davr

<https://www.trt.net.tr/uzbek/turk-dunyosi/2022/12/23/01234567890-330-1922800>